

NANO-BIO-COMPOSITE MECHANICS: RECENT EXPERIMENTS

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1 General Introduction

With the development of composites based on micrometer-sized fibers, the second half of the twentieth century witnessed a vast transformation in the engineering, design and performance of structural materials. An excellent example of this can be seen in the materials used in two new super-jets — the Airbus 380 and Boeing 787 Dreamliner. The wings and fuselage of these airplanes consist of an unprecedented amount — up to 50% by weight — of composite materials, enabling substantial weight savings and much improved aerodynamic efficiency. Now, with the emergence of nanometer-sized particles (such as platelets, fibers and tubes), the probability of a second revolution in composites is high.

Nanocomposites are currently the subject of extensive worldwide research. These include synthetic materials — in which a ‘soft’ polymer matrix is reinforced with ‘hard’ fillers such as exfoliated sheets of clay, graphite flakes or carbon nanotubes (CNTs) — as well as biological composites found in nature, such as bone, wood or shells.

This paper deals with some of our recent results and relevant techniques for the testing of very small objects belonging to various areas, for example carbon and tungsten sulfide nanotubes in the composites area, and bone and dentin specimens in biology. Some of our recent experimental and theoretical results regarding materials mechanics at the nanoscale will be reviewed [1-9]. The main theme includes carbon and tungsten sulfide nanotubes, and nanotube-based composite materials. Such developments still present, however, enormous practical challenges, in particular: (1) when attempting to probe the properties of individual nanotubes, for which most –but not all- studies

consist of computer simulations, and (2) when attempting to optimize the mechanical properties of nanocomposites, especially biological nanocomposites [10-12]. We report here our most recent laboratory results regarding polymer-nanotube composite mechanics, including interfacial adhesion and toughness issues, as well as mechanical testing and theoretical modeling of staggered biological composite structures.

2 Carbon Nanotube-Based Nanocomposites

A particularly simple and appealing approach to prepare large-scale, aligned, hierarchical nanocomposites in fibrous form is the electrospinning process, a technique used in applications such as filters, membranes, scaffolding for biotissue build-up, clothing, and more. In recent years electrospinning was used to prepare SWCNT and MWCNT reinforced polyacrylonitrile fibers, MWCNT reinforced poly(ethylene oxide), and MWCNT reinforced poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) [5, 8, and references therein]. This submicrometer fiber formation process has the marked benefit that carbon nanotubes are necessarily confined to an aligned configuration parallel to the fiber axis. A wide range of polymers can be used, and achievable diameters range from several nanometers to a few micrometers. Submicrometer fibers made of pure PMMA, and of PMMA reinforced with both pristine SWCNTs and pristine MWCNTs (CNT/PMMA weight ratio of 1.5% in the initial composite dispersion), were electrospun (ES) in our laboratory using a procedure described elsewhere [5,8]. The morphologies of fractured nanotube-reinforced PMMA ES fibers can be seen in Figure 1. The surface of the fibers is generally smooth and the cross section is uniform along the fiber length. Most nanotubes embedded in the fiber

are indeed aligned along the fiber axis; SWCNTs exist as long and thick ropes within the fiber, whereas MWCNTs are well separated and dispersed lengthwise, in the fiber bulk.

Fig.1. TEM images of stretched PMMA with MWCNT (left) and SWCNT (right) electrospun fibers.

The fibers were tested in tension using a homemade nanotensile tester mounted on an inverted optical microscope. We tested 17, 20, and 19 electrospun fibers of PMMA, PMMA/MWCNTs, and PMMA/SWCNTs, respectively. The strength data were fitted to a standard two-parameter Weibull distribution. The resulting Weibull scale parameters were 118, 148, and 92 MPa, and the Weibull shape parameters were 2.0, 1.7, and 1.7 for PMMA, PMMA/MWCNTs, and PMMA/SWCNTs, respectively. The low values of the shape parameters reflect the large variability in strength in all cases. The slightly lower shape parameters of the composite fibers indicate larger strength variability compared to that of pure PMMA fibers. To eliminate in the present work unwanted variability due to any diameter effect, we selected a subset of specimens with a diameter restricted to 500-750 nm only.

The addition of CNTs causes a striking, visible transformation in the deformation mode of PMMA ES fibers. In pure PMMA fibers, sparse and unstable polymer necking occurs under increasing tension, leading to failure at relatively small strains. However, the presence of either SWCNTs or MWCNTs causes the failure strain to reach comparatively enormous values, due to the overwhelming occurrence of stable polymer necking all along the fibers. This is clearly observed in movies of the tests. This effect seems counterintuitive at first, as one would expect a strong and stiff oblate reinforcement to compel a polymer specimen to fail at smaller rather than larger strains.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) provides clues to the root causes of the much larger fiber deformation observed when CNTs are present in the PMMA fibers, as compared to PMMA-only specimens. In PMMA/MWCNT ES fibers, Figure 1 shows that following localized polymer necking leading to polymer failure, extensive MWCNT pull-out takes place. Such double mechanisms -necking followed by pull-out- involves large inelastic strains and extensive energy dissipation. However, in PMMA/SWCNT ES fibers a different double mechanism arises, as shown in Figure 1. In this case, multiple necking of the fiber proceeds until it is prevented from further growth by the presence of SWCNTs ropes which act as a deflecting wall. The polymer molecules then likely slip and align by shearing along the ropes, leading to the bridging structures observed by TEM and again (but for a different reason than that with MWCNTs) to very large inelastic deformations. Interestingly enough, increases in deformation and toughness -but not strength or stiffness- due to the presence of CNTs are also observed in millimeter-size PMMA films albeit to a lesser extent because of the absence of polymer necking in films [5]. Thus, significant toughness enhancements, in films and mostly in nanofibers, due to the presence of both types of CNTs, are the truly significant observation here. Qualitative observations of deformation by necking and occasional fibrillation were also reported during the preparation (rather than during controlled tensile testing) of ES poly(ethylene oxide) fibers and by crazing followed by pull-out in nanotube-reinforced polyacrylonitrile fibers. No crazing or fibrillation was observed here. The mechanical properties of the fibers measured by nanotensile testing are impressive especially in view -and perhaps because- of the fact that the nanotubes of both types possess no adhesion-enhancing functional groups at their surface. To verify that no functional groups (such as carboxylic acid) were present on the surface of the MWCNTs, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) data for pristine MWCNTs were compared with those for carboxylated MWCNTs (obtained from the same source, the surface treatment being based on the same pristine MWCNTs). A significant difference in the oxygen content could be observed between the pristine MWCNTs ([O] ~ 0.95%, most probably originating from residual water absorbed on the surface) and the carboxylated MWCNTs ([O]

~ 3.5%). In a separate study (not discussed in the present paper) we performed mechanical tests with PMMA/COOH-MWCNTs. The results were significantly different than those presented here with pristine MWCNTs. For example, the average strain was $43.3 \pm 15.2\%$ (compared to 80.6% here) and the average tensile strength was 78.3 ± 14.2 MPa (compared to 194 MPa here). This is an additional indication that COOH groups were not present on the tubes used here. The Young's modulus of MWCNT-based fibers is three times as high as that of the PMMA fibers (it is even slightly above the value obtained for macroscopic films). The modulus of SWCNT-based fibers is about the same as that of PMMA fibers, most likely because in this case the reinforcement consists of thick and tight ropes of SWCNTs rather than of well-dispersed tubes. Indeed, it is known that the modulus of SWCNT ropes strongly decreases with increasing rope diameter (a 30 nm diameter SWCNT rope has a Young's modulus of less than 70 GPa whereas in comparison, well-dispersed individual SWCNTs and MWCNTs have moduli of ~ 1000 and ~ 500 GPa, respectively). We used bath sonication for 1 h for both nanocomposite types as an attempt to break down the agglomerates of SWCNTs and MWCNTs and to debundle the SWCNT ropes. This was generally enough to de-agglomerate the CNTs but not enough to debundle the SWCNTs ropes. Longer/stronger sonication is known to induce severe defects and to break the CNTs, leading to a significant degradation of the mechanical properties, and thus was avoided here. Compared to tensile tests previously performed in the environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM) chamber with the same materials, the specimens tested here in standard laboratory conditions (in air, at room temperature) all show significantly higher strength and stiffness, and generally lower strain to failure [5]. Moreover, the relative variability in these parameters, reflected in percent by the coefficient of variation (standard deviation divided by the mean), which is always high when testing submicrometer fibers, is significantly lower in the present case compared to tests performed in the ESEM. These observations are obviously due to the absence of any of the destructive effects of the electron beam on the polymer structure which are observed when tests are performed in an ESEM. If absolute values of

mechanical properties are desired, this effectively precludes testing of ES fibers in the ESEM.

A final remarkable point is the difference in properties and in variability between submicrometer ES fibers and millimeter-size films made with the same PMMA-based materials. This issue is somewhat more complex: (i) The strength of ES fibers (of all three types) is significantly higher (by a factor of almost 4 when MWCNTs are present) than the strength of films. Apart from the distinct preparation methods, this difference is likely due to two causes, the widely different scales of the specimens (fiber diameters are about 500 nm, film thicknesses are about 100 μm), as thinner specimens usually have much larger strength, and the fact that CNTs as well as the polymer molecules are well-aligned within the electrospun fiber bulk, whereas they are randomly dispersed in the films. (ii) The failure strain of ES fibers is always much higher than that of films, due to the nucleation and growth of localized, stable polymer necking regions forming in fibers but not in films. (iii) The resulting toughness of ES fibers, calculated here simply as the area under the stress-strain curve, is always much higher than the toughness of films, reflecting the differences in strain. (iv) However the Young's modulus of ES fibers is almost always smaller (or at best equal, when MWCNTs are present) than the film modulus. For all properties, the relative variability is generally slightly higher for fibers than for films, mainly in the case of SWCNT-based specimens but the cause of this is not clear. Points ii-iv deserve some further clarification. The origin of extensive necking in CNT-reinforced PMMA fibers is in part mechanical, arising from perturbations caused by local stress concentrations at the edges of the aligned nanotubes in the fibers, and in part molecular, arising from molecular entanglements which serve as virtual crosslinks, both being a source of local perturbation. Extensive necking leads to enhanced toughness in ES fibers but not in films because no necking is present in these. At the same time a lower Young's modulus is generally observed in ES fibers, compared to films. This can be explained by a simple molecular argument based on recent thermal tests performed in our laboratory (but not shown here *in extenso*). In addition to a typical glass transition temperature (T_g), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) tests of PMMA ES fibers also reveal a significant endothermic peak at

about 60 °C, whereas this peak is altogether absent in films of the same material. Assuming that, through the electrospinning process, the molecular backbone of PMMA is stretched and oriented along the fiber axis, the probability of slippage between parallel polymer chains increases, compared to the entangled morphology in films. In films, no such transition is observed in the DSC curve, and no interchain slippage is present: Young's modulus is higher and the strain is lower because they are dominated by the breakage of C-C bonds. Note that the DSC curves of the PMMA/MWCNTs and PMMA/SWCNTs composite ES fibers are identical to that of the pure PMMA fiber because the low filler content (1.5 wt %) does not affect the thermal properties.

Fig.2. The load–deformation traces generated in HRSEM compression tests of multilayered polyhedral nanoparticles. The stiffness is obtained by calculating the load/deformation ratio of the linear regression lines.

3 Tungsten Disulfide Nanotube-Based Nanocomposites

Measurements conducted on individual inorganic multilayered polyhedral nanoparticles are challenging and complex. Our recent paper [9] describes a new technique for in-situ axial nanocompression of individual nanoparticles in an HRSEM. The technique could be extended to other nanoparticles. From this new technique the compression failure strength and stiffness were evaluated (Fig. 2). Layered inorganic materials, such

as WS₂ and MoS₂, that form seamless hollow closed nanostructures are, due to their small size and layered structure, able to withstand very high elastic stress. Despite the fact that the faceted shape of the nanoparticles leads to the stress being concentrated at the corners, the compression failure strength of these nanoparticles is as high as 1–2.5 GPa. The stiffness of the faceted nanoparticles is found to be lower than that of a spherical nanoparticle, due to higher stress concentration at the corners. Future work in this direction will focus on the systematic study of the mechanical properties of hollow closed cage nanoparticles of different kinds and on possible optimization of their mechanical behavior.

4 Hard Biological Tissues

We have recently studied the effective moduli of multi-scale hard biological tissues comprising a staggered reinforcement in at least one of their scales [10-12]. At first, an expression for the effective elastic modulus of a staggered platelet-matrix composite is formulated in terms of the platelet volume fraction, aspect ratio and thickness ratio. The effective modulus is solved for a variety of platelet dimensions, from which it is concluded that thicker platelets result in higher modulus than longer ones. It is also shown that the modulus coincides with Gao's formula (see reference in [12]) for the corresponding asymptotic limits. The effective modulus is then evaluated for selected biological structures and compared with experimental and finite element results from the literature. The expression proposed in [12] provides an improved evaluation of the elastic modulus, compared to other models. A bundle of unidirectional collagen fibrils with uncorrelated rolling angles is studied next. Each fibril within the bundle exhibits orthotropic properties, however the bundle itself is transversally isotropic with only two independent moduli, parallel and perpendicular to the bundle direction. The parallel modulus is higher than the perpendicular one, and is affected by the fibril length. Finally, the multi-scale structure of dentin, viewed here as a tubular array embedded in an anisotropic matrix, is analyzed by adapting traditional composite mechanics. We use experimental literature data for the tubules concentration gradient to demonstrate that, under

certain conditions, a transition from structural isotropy to anisotropy arises across the dentin region, from the pulp to the DEJ.

Fig.3. Schematic description of a bundle of unidirectional collagen fibrils with uncorrelated roll angles, arranged in a staggered structure inside an extrafibrillar matrix. The bundle is transversally isotropic with two Young moduli, along and perpendicular to the bundle orientation.

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6 References

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